

Ultrasonic and Viscometric Studies of Yttrium Soap in Mixed Organic Solvents

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The ultrasonic and viscosity measurements of yttrium soaps (caprylate, caprate and laurate) in a mixture of benzene and dimethyl formamide (3 : 2) have been carried out with a view to determine the critical micellar concentration, soap-solvent interaction and other allied parameters. The various acoustic parameters (intermolecular free length, adiabatic compressibility, apparent molar compressibility, specific acoustic impedance, molar sound velocity, solvation number, available volume and relative association) have been evaluated by ultrasonic velocity measurements. The results of viscosity measurements have been explained in terms of well known equations.

Molecular and ion-solvent interactions have been studied using various techniques¹. The variation of ultrasonic velocity and various acoustic parameters with temperature have been studied by using the diffraction technique². The propagation of ultrasonic wave and the measurements of its velocity³ and absorption⁴ in inorganic, and organometallic binary systems have been used to determine the nature of molecular interactions in these systems. Several workers⁵ used ultrasonic velocity measurements for studying ion-solvent interactions. The viscosity of the solutions of lanthanide, uranyl and transition metal soaps have been determined by various workers⁶.

The present work deals with the ultrasonic velocity and viscosity measurements of the solutions of yttrium soaps (caprylate, caprate and laurate) in a mixture of benzene and dimethyl formamide (3 : 2). The results have been used to study the soap solvent interaction and to evaluate the CMC and various acoustic parameters.

Results and Discussion

Ultrasonic measurements: The ultrasonic velocity (v) in solutions of yttrium soaps in a mixture of benzene and dimethyl formamide (3 : 2) increases with increasing concentration of soap (Table 1). The variation of velocity with solute molarity can be expressed by the relationship,

$$\frac{dv}{dC} = -\frac{v}{2} [1/\rho(d\rho/dC) + 1/\beta(d\beta/dC)]$$

The results show that while the density increases, the adiabatic compressibility decreases with increasing soap concentration. Therefore, the quantity $(d\rho/dC)$ is positive while $(d\beta/dC)$ is negative. Since the factor $(1/\beta(d\beta/dC))$ predominates over the factor $(1/\rho(d\rho/dC))$ for yttrium soap solutions, the values of the quantity (dv/dC) will be positive, and so the velocity increases with increasing soap concentration.

The results are in agreement with that for electrolytic solutions⁷.

The variation in ultrasonic velocity (v) with the concentration of the soap solution (C) follows the relationship,

$$v = v_0 + GC$$

where v_0 is the ultrasonic velocity in pure solvent and G is Garnsey's constant. The plots v against C (Fig. 1) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration, which corresponds to the CMC of the soap solution (caprylate, 0.0130 M; caprate, 0.0120 M; laurate, 0.0113 M). The values of G for the yttrium soaps are 5.5×10^6 , 6.0×10^6 and 7.2×10^6 for caprylate, caprate and laurate, respectively.

The adiabatic compressibility (β) of yttrium soap solutions decreases with increase in the soap concentration, as well as with increase in the chainlength of fatty acid constituent of the soap molecule. The complimentary use of adiabatic compressibility data can provide interesting information on ion-solvent interaction and the structure of solute. The plots of β vs C also exhibit a break at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soap solutions. The plots of β vs C are extrapolated to zero soap concentration and the extrapolated value (6.378×10^{-11} cm² dyne⁻¹) is in agreement with the experimental one (6.359×10^{-11} cm² dyne⁻¹) indicating that the soap molecules exist as monomers in dilute solution below the CMC and there is no appreciable aggregation between the soap molecules. The results of adiabatic compressibility have been explained in terms of Bachem's equation⁸.

$$\beta = \beta_0 + AC + BC^{3/2}$$

where β_0 is the compressibility of the solvent, C the concentration and A and B are constants. The values of A (-19.3×10^{-10} , -15.2×10^{-10} and -17.5×10^{-10} for caprylate, caprate and laurate

TABLE 1—ULTRASONIC VELOCITY AND OTHER ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF YTTRIUM SOAPS IN A MIXTURE OF 60% BENZENE AND 40% DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE

Sl. no.	$C \times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	ρ g ml ⁻¹	$v \times 10^{-3}$ cm/sec	$\beta_0 \times 10^{11}$ cm dyne ⁻¹	L_f λ	$Z \times 10^{-4}$ (C.G.S.)
Caprylate						
1.	2.5	0.903 6	1.328	0.295	0.098 25	
2.	5.0	0.903 7	1.328	0.276	0.087 61	1.198
3.	7.5	0.904 1	1.330	0.253	0.097 40	1.200
4.	10.0	0.904 3	1.331	0.242	0.097 29	1.203
5.	12.5	0.904 6	1.332	0.231	0.097 20	1.204
6.	15.0	0.905 0	1.335	0.200	0.097 11	1.205
7.	17.5	0.905 4	1.338	0.170	0.096 87	1.208
8.	20.0	0.905 8	1.341	0.130	0.096 61	1.211
9.	22.5	0.906 2	1.344	0.109	0.096 40	1.215
10.	25.0	0.906 7	1.348	0.07	0.096 18	1.218
Caprate						
1.	2.5	0.904 0	1.329	6.263	0.095 85	1.201
2.	5.0	0.904 2	1.331	6.243	0.097 36	1.204
3.	7.5	0.904 6	1.333	6.221	0.097 21	1.204
4.	10.0	0.904 8	1.335	6.201	0.097 04	1.208
5.	12.5	0.905 2	1.337	6.180	0.096 88	1.210
6.	15.0	0.905 6	1.341	6.141	0.096 72	1.214
7.	17.5	0.906 1	1.346	6.092	0.096 02	1.220
8.	20.0	0.906 5	1.350	6.053	0.096 02	1.224
9.	22.5	0.907 0	1.354	6.014	0.095 72	1.228
10.	25.0	0.907 4	1.358	6.076	0.095 41	1.232
Laurate						
1.	2.5	0.904 2	1.331	6.243	0.095 11	1.204
2.	5.0	0.904 6	1.334	6.212	0.097 21	1.207
3.	7.5	0.905 1	1.336	6.190	0.096 17	1.209
4.	10.0	0.905 4	1.338	6.170	0.096 79	1.211
5.	12.5	0.906 0	1.342	6.129	0.096 64	1.216
6.	15.0	0.906 5	1.347	6.060	0.095 93	1.221
7.	17.5	0.907 1	1.352	6.031	0.095 54	1.226
8.	20.0	0.907 6	1.356	5.992	0.095 23	1.231
9.	22.5	0.908 2	1.362	5.938	0.094 79	1.237
10.	25.0	0.908 8	1.367	5.888	0.094 40	1.242

Fig. 1 Ultrasonic velocity vs concentration of yttrium soaps in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% dimethylformamide: (A) caprylate, (Δ) caprate and (O) laurate.

soap) and B (7.5×10^{-3} , 8.2×10^{-3} and 12.5×10^{-3} for caprylate, caprate and laurate soap) were

obtained from the intercept and slope of the plots of $(\beta - \beta_0/C)$ vs $C^{1/2}$ for the soap solutions.

The plots of apparent molar compressibility, (ϕ_k) against $C^{1/2}$ are characterised by the intersection of two straight lines at the CMC. These plots have been extrapolated to obtain the values of limiting apparent molar compressibility, ϕ_k^0 (-4.5×10^{-7} , -5.0×10^{-7} and -8.1×10^{-7} for caprylate, caprate and laurate, respectively). It follows from the Debye-Hückel theory that the apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) is related to the molar concentration of the soap (C) by the relationship,

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k C^{1/2}$$

where ϕ_k^0 is the limiting apparent molar compressibility and S_k is a constant. The values of S_k (0.84×10^{-7} , 0.98×10^{-7} and 12.3×10^{-7} for caprylate, caprate and laurate, respectively) have been calculated from the slope of these plots and compared with the results for different electrolytes.

The intermolecular free length (L_f) decreases while the specific acoustic impedance (Z) increases with an increase in the soap concentration, and with the chainlength of the soap (Table 1). This

TABLE 2—APPARENT MOLAR COMPRESSIBILITY AND OTHER PARAMETERS OF YTTRIUM SOAPS IN A MIXTURE OF 60% BENZENE AND 40% DIMETHYL FORMAMIDE

Sl. no.	$C \times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$-\phi_K \times 10^3$	R_A	$R \times 10^{-4}$	V_s	S_n
<i>Caprylate</i>						
1.	2.5	3.208	0.999 0	4.298	14.87	61
2.	5.0	1.847	0.998 7	4.304	14.55	39
3.	7.5	1.440	0.998 6	4.310	14.36	31
4.	10.0	1.112	0.998 6	4.316	14.23	25
5.	12.5	0.920	0.998 7	4.320	14.17	22
6.	15.0	0.831	0.998 4	4.327	14.02	21
7.	17.5	0.833	0.998 1	4.333	13.89	22
8.	20.0	0.830	0.997 8	4.340	13.73	22
9.	22.5	0.940	0.997 6	4.346	13.58	22
10.	25.0	0.970	0.997 0	4.354	13.37	23
<i>Caprate</i>						
1.	2.5	4.568	0.998 8	4.299	14.27	66
2.	5.0	2.499	0.998 5	4.307	14.18	50
3.	7.5	1.854	0.998 4	4.313	14.09	39
4.	10.0	1.497	0.998 2	4.321	14.00	33
5.	12.5	1.303	0.998 1	4.327	13.90	30
6.	15.0	1.293	0.997 6	4.336	13.71	29
7.	17.5	1.348	0.995 9	4.346	13.46	30
8.	20.0	1.335	0.996 3	4.354	13.26	30
9.	22.5	1.328	0.995 9	4.425	13.06	30
10.	25.0	1.316	0.995 4	4.371	12.86	30
<i>Laurate</i>						
1.	2.5	5.365	0.998 5	4.302	14.16	90
2.	5.0	3.116	0.998 2	4.311	14.02	62
3.	7.5	2.255	0.998 3	4.317	13.93	47
4.	10.0	1.790	0.998 1	4.321	13.85	39
5.	12.5	1.697	0.997 8	4.334	13.65	37
6.	15.0	1.693	0.997 1	4.344	13.41	37
7.	17.5	1.677	0.996 5	4.354	13.15	37
8.	20.0	1.619	0.996 1	4.363	12.95	36
9.	22.5	1.653	0.995 8	4.374	12.65	37
10.	25.0	1.648	0.994 7	4.384	12.39	37

indicates that there is a significant interaction between the solute and solvent molecules due to which the structural arrangement is considerably affected. The increase in the values of Z with increasing soap concentration can be explained on the basis of lyophobic interaction between soap and solvent molecules which increases the intermolecular distance making relatively wider gaps between the molecules and becoming the main cause of impedance in the propagation of ultrasound waves. The plots of L_s and Z against C show a break indicating the CMC of the soap.

The values of available volume (V_s) and relative association (R_A) decrease with increasing soap concentration (Table 2). The plots of V_s and R_A vs soap concentration (C) are characterised by a break at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of the soap. The decrease in the values of relative association with increasing soap concentration is attributed to the fact that the solvation of ions decreases with increasing soap concentration.

The molar sound velocity (R) increases whereas the solvation number (S_n) decreases with increase in the soap concentration. The metal soap is largely present as metal cations and fatty acid anions

in dilute solutions. The ions are surrounded by a layer of solvent molecules firmly bound and oriented towards ions. The orientation of solvent molecules around the ions may be due to the influence of electrostatic field of ions. The higher values of solvation number suggest a significant interaction between solvent-soap molecules and the values are in agreement with the reported results for solutions of cobalt carboxylates⁹.

It may be concluded that yttrium soaps behave as simple electrolytes in dilute solutions and the electrostrictive effect of the ions on the polar solvent (DMF) molecules in the immediate vicinity of the ions is greater than on non-polar solvent (benzene) molecules. The results confirm that there is a significant interaction between soap-solvent molecules in dilute solutions.

Viscosity measurements: The viscosity (η) and specific viscosity (η_{sp}) of the solutions of yttrium soaps increase with the increasing soap concentration (Table 3). This increase may be due to the increasing tendency of the soap molecules to form aggregates with increasing soap concentration. The plots of η against C are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at the CMC of the soap (caprylate, 0.0130 M ; caprate, 0.0120 M ;

TABLE 3 - VISCOSITY MEASUREMENTS OF YTTRIUM SOAPS IN A MIXTURE OF 60% BENZENE AND 40% DIMETHYL FORMAMIDE

Sl. No.	Concn. (g/l)	η_{sp}/C (ml ² g ⁻¹)	$\eta_{sp}/\sqrt{C}$	η_{sp}/C	$\eta_{sp}/\sqrt{C}$	η_{sp}/C	$(\eta/\eta_0)^{1/2}$	η/η_0
Capyrate								
1.	2.5	0.983 5	0.105 6	17.13	0.348 6	6.972	1.135	133.58
2.	5.0	0.983 7	0.667 2	19.87	0.275 0	3.971	1.141	117.1
3.	7.5	0.984 1	0.880 1	23.23	0.267 0	3.097	1.047	110.25
4.	10.0	0.984 2	0.871 0	25.08	0.256 8	2.588	1.052	91.8
5.	12.5	0.984 8	0.872 2	27.52	0.245 7	2.202	1.056	84.58
6.	15.0	0.985 0	0.677 4	35.40	0.289 3	2.361	1.072	60.17
7.	17.5	0.985 4	0.611 0	41.88	0.317 3	2.393	1.086	56.1
8.	20.0	0.985 8	0.684 8	40.78	0.331 8	2.339	1.096	50.37
9.	22.5	0.986 2	0.688 5	52.43	0.349 5	2.330	1.103	45.16
10.	25.0	0.986 7	0.692 8	59.00	0.373 4	2.369	1.122	40.17
Caprate								
1.	2.5	0.984 0	0.670 3	21.61	0.492 2	9.844	1.059	94.71
2.	5.0	0.984 2	0.671 9	27.06	0.381 1	5.412	1.055	86.25
3.	7.5	0.984 6	0.675 1	31.95	0.367 2	4.260	1.065	73.22
4.	10.0	0.984 8	0.678 2	36.69	0.366 9	3.669	1.075	63.91
5.	12.5	0.985 2	0.681 4	41.58	0.371 3	3.326	1.085	56.52
6.	15.0	0.985 6	0.685 1	47.23	0.383 9	3.149	1.097	49.69
7.	17.5	0.986 1	0.689 9	54.57	0.413 4	3.118	1.112	43.34
8.	20.0	0.986 5	0.694 6	61.76	0.438 0	3.088	1.127	38.43
9.	22.5	0.987 0	0.698 8	68.18	0.454 5	3.030	1.141	34.81
10.	25.0	0.987 4	0.701 6	71.46	0.458 6	2.898	1.150	32.92
Laurate								
1.	2.5	0.984 2	0.673 9	30.11	0.602 2	12.044	1.161	77.61
2.	5.0	0.984 6	0.676 6	34.24	0.482 3	6.848	1.070	68.59
3.	7.5	0.985 1	0.679 9	39.29	0.451 6	5.239	1.080	59.76
4.	10.0	0.985 4	0.683 0	44.02	0.440 2	4.402	1.090	53.45
5.	12.5	0.986 0	0.685 4	47.69	0.425 8	3.815	1.098	49.42
6.	15.0	0.986 5	0.690 7	55.79	0.453 6	3.719	1.115	42.41
7.	17.5	0.987 1	0.694 0	60.84	0.460 9	3.477	1.125	38.99
8.	20.0	0.987 6	0.697 2	65.89	0.467 2	3.294	1.136	36.19
9.	22.5	0.988 2	0.702 7	74.14	0.494 3	3.295	1.154	32.20
10.	25.0	0.708 8	0.705 6	78.57	0.497 3	3.143	1.163	30.44

laurate, 0.0115 M). The viscosity results confirm that there is no appreciable aggregation of the soap molecules below the CMC whereas there is marked change in the aggregation at this soap concentration.

The viscosity results have been interpreted in the light of equations proposed by Einstein¹⁰, Vand¹¹, Moulík¹² and Jones-Dole¹³,

Einstein: $\eta_{sp} = 2.5 \phi C$

Vand: $1/C = \left(\frac{0.921}{V} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\log \eta/\eta_0} \right) + \phi V$

Moulík: $(\eta/\eta_0)^2 = M + KC^2$

Jones-Dole: $\eta_{sp}/C = A + BC$

where V , C , ϕ , η , η_0 and η_{sp} are the molar volume, concentration of the soap, interaction coefficient, viscosity of solution, viscosity of solvent and specific viscosity, respectively, M and K are Moulík's and A and B refer to Jones-Dole's constants. The plots of η_{sp} against C are linear below the CMC with the intercept almost equal to zero which shows that Einstein's equation is applicable to dilute solutions of yttrium soaps in the benzene-DMF mixture. The

Fig. 2. Viscosity vs concentration of yttrium soaps in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% dimethyl formamide: (●) caprylate, (Δ) caprate and (○) laurate.

values of molar volume (0.34, 0.38 and 0.40 mol⁻¹ for caprylate, caprate and laurate, respectively) of

the soap calculated from slope of Einstein's plots are in agreement with the values obtained from the slope of Vand's plots.

The plots of $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ against C^2 show a break at a definite soap concentration corresponding to the CMC of the soap (caprylate, 0.0134 *M*; caprate, 0.0114 *M*; laurate, 0.0105 *M*). The plots are linear below the CMC which shows that the Moulik's equation is applicable to dilute solutions of yttrium soaps in benzene DMF mixture. The values of Moulik's constants, M (caprylate, 1.14; caprate, 1.25; laurate, 1.37) and K (caprylate, 301; caprate, 232; laurate, 241) have been obtained from the intercept and slope of these plots, respectively. The viscosity data have also been explained in the light of Jones-Dole's equation. The values of the constants A (0.31, 0.38 and 0.46 for caprylate, caprate and laurate, respectively) and B (1.51, 1.92 and 3.11 for caprylate, caprate and laurate, respectively) have been calculated from the intercept and slope of the plots of η_{sp}/C vs C for the solutions of yttrium soaps. The small values of constant A again confirm that there is no appreciable aggregation in dilute soap solutions below the CMC. The values of constant B (soap-solvent interaction) differ widely below and above the CMC. This may be attributed to the fact that the aggregation of the soap molecules above the CMC boosts up the electrokinetic forces causing more intake of the solvent resulting in the increasing viscosity of the system.

The values $1/\log \eta/\eta_0$ have been used to calculate the molar volume from linear plots of $1/\log \eta/\eta_0$ vs $1/C$ for dilute soap solutions. The values of molar volume, $\bar{V}$ (0.33, 0.39 and 0.421 mol⁻¹ for caprylate, caprate and laurate soap) and interaction coefficient, ϕ (8.0) have been calculated from the slope and intercept of these plots, respectively.

The density, viscosity and ultrasonic measurements of the solutions of yttrium soaps in a mixture of benzene and dimethyl formamide (3 : 2) were used to determine the critical micelle concentration of the soaps and the results were explained in terms of well-known equations. The values of CMC and the molar volume of the soap obtained by using these equations are in agreement. It is, therefore, concluded that the viscosity results for solutions of yttrium soaps may be satisfactorily explained in terms of these equations.

Experimental

Chemicals used were A.R./G.R. (E. Merck) grade. The yttrium soaps (caprylate, caprate and laurate) were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soaps with the required amount of aqueous solution of yttrium nitrate at 50–55° under vigorous stirring. The precipitated soaps were washed with distilled water and acetone to remove the excess of metal ions and unreacted fatty acids. The purity of the soap was checked by elemental analysis and the experimental results

were found to be in agreement with the theoretically calculated values. The reproducibility of the results was checked by preparing two samples of the same soap under similar conditions. The absence of hydroxyl group in the soaps was confirmed by their ir spectra.

The ultrasonic velocity of the solutions of yttrium soaps was measured by the multifrequency ultrasonic interferometer (M-83 Mittal Enterprises) at a frequency of 1 MHz at a constant temperature (40 ± 0.05°). The densities of the solvent and solutions were measured with a dilatometer calibrated with pure benzene. Ostwald's type viscometer was used for measuring the viscosity.

The various acoustic parameters, viz. intermolecular free-length (L_f)¹⁴, adiabatic compressibility (β), specific acoustic impedance (Z)¹⁵, apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K), molar sound velocity (R), solvation number (S_n)¹⁶, available volume (V_a)¹⁷ and relative association (R_A)¹⁸ have been evaluated by using following relationships,

$$L_f = (\beta/K)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$\beta = V^{-2} \rho^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$$Z = V\rho \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_K = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\rho_0\beta - \beta_0\rho) + \frac{\beta_0 M}{\rho_0} \quad (4)$$

$$R = \frac{\bar{M}}{\rho} v^{1/3} \quad (5)$$

$$\left[\bar{M} = \frac{n_0 M_0 + nM}{n_0 + n} \right]$$

$$S_n = \frac{n_0}{n} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{V}\beta}{n_0 \bar{V}_0 \beta_0} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$V_a = \bar{V} \left(1 - \frac{v}{v_\infty} \right) \quad (7)$$

and

$$R_A = (\rho/\rho_0)(v_0/v)^{1/3} \quad (8)$$

where v_0 , v ; ρ_0 , ρ ; β_0 , β and $\bar{V}_0$, $\bar{V}$ are the ultrasonic velocity, density, adiabatic compressibility and molar volume of the solvent and solution respectively, n_0 , n and M_0 , M are the number of moles and molecular weight of solvent and solute respectively, and K and C are the temperature dependent Jacobson's constant and concentration respectively, v_∞ is equivalent to 1 600 ms⁻¹.

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